

ISic0823

Statue base for Hieron II of Syracuse

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone (area of Taormina?)

Object

statue base

Editor

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6489

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Βασιλέος ἀγε[μόνος]
2. Ἱέρωνος Ἱεροκλέος
3. Συρακόσιοι θεοῖς πᾶσι

Apparatus

Text of Kaibel (IG)

ἀγε[ομένου], Dittenberger

Translation (en)

The Syracusans (dedicate this statue) of the king and hegemon Hieron, son of Hierokles, to all the gods

Commentary

As John Ma, *Statues and Cities* (Oxford 2013) 20 n.27 notes, this is an anomalous instance of an honorific dedication where the honorand is in the genitive

Digital identifiers:

TM 285056
EDR 114423
EDCS 39101971
PHI 140291

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0002 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 56.1103.1.1
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5368
- Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezzenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 3231
- Dittenberger, W. 1915-1924. Sylloge inscriptionum graecarum. Leipzig. At no.427
- De Sensi Sestito, G. 1977. Gerone II. Un monarca ellenistico in Sicilia. *Kleio.* Palermo. At 82
- Libertini, G 1929. Il regio museo archeologico di Siracusa. *Guide dei musei italiani.* Roma. At 123
- Dimartino, A. 2006. Per una revisione dei documenti epigrafici siracusani pertinenti al regno di Ierone II. In Michelini, C.(eds.), *Guerra e pace in Sicilia e nel Mediterraneo antico (VIII-III sec. a.C.). Arte, prassi e teoria della pace e della guerra.* Pisa. pp. 703-717. At no.1.1
- Prag, J.R.W. 2017. Un unpublished funerary inscription with bichrome painted relief lettering from Hellenistic Syracuse (I.Sicily 3387). *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik.* 203: 119-130. At 122 fig.5

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014